

‘Cover Your Drink!’ - A Critical Discourse
Analysis of the Responsibilisation of
Women in Spiking Awareness Posters.

Freya Carr

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Abstract

The nighttime environment can be viewed as a fun social setting to enjoy a drink with friends, but it soon feels dangerous as the threat of spiking looms over women. This gendered environment, where women are repeatedly urged to look after themselves and prevent themselves from being needle spiked or having their drink spiked, has become an unsafe place where women can no longer enjoy themselves without the danger of spiking presenting itself. Expanding on current research on spiking in the night-time economy (NTE), specifically in relation to women – who have been proven to be more likely to fall victim to this crime – this research investigates how women are responsabilised to protect themselves from spiking and how perpetrators hold much less responsibility than potential victims. The Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) of spiking awareness posters, which were collected for this research, looked closely at the presentations, language, and truth modalities of the posters, and how these combined factors responsabilised women as a result. The analysis showed that women are much more likely to be responsabilised in spiking awareness posters than men, with the force of gendered stereotypes coming into play – resultantly expressing the burden which women, as a group, must face in being their own forms of crime prevention to protect themselves, and each other, from spiking attacks. With women often being told how to behave and how to look after themselves in the NTE, these outside factors have detrimental effects on how women perceive their safety and how responsible they are for it. More research is needed, to further fully understand the extent of this issue, however this research will still unpack the issues surrounding women being responsabilised in potential spiking scenarios, and the consequences of this.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

'Spiking' is known as the act of administering a substance to someone without a lack of consent, and it can be perpetrated in the form of drink spiking, or needle spiking (Home Office, 2024). In England, one single offence does not wholly cover spiking, instead, it is illegal under multiple legislations, including the Offences Against the Person Act 1861 and the Sexual offences Act 2003 (Lipscombe, 2023). According to the National Police Chief's Council (NPCC), the Police receive an average of 561 reports of spiking per month but given that spiking is known to be under-reported, partly due to detrimental myths and stereotypes which prevent victims from speaking up (NPCC, 2024a), this figure is likely much higher. With the majority of these reports coming from female victims who have had their drink spiked (Home Office, 2024), this research aims to explore how women are responsabilised, disturbingly more than men, to prevent spiking attacks, particularly in the NTE. This dissertation aims to problematise the issue of women being faced with the burden of protecting themselves from spiking in the gendered NTE (Stevenson, 2018), with no responsibility seeming to be allocated to perpetrators. Due to this research being a CDA of the responsabilisation of women in spiking awareness posters, it subsequently has an issue-oriented nature rather than being question-oriented – as CDA tends to focus on research issues (van Dijk, 2009). Therefore, instead of having a research question, this dissertation rather highlights the issues being unpacked, in relation to women being responsabilised to protect themselves from spiking attacks and the pressures that they must endure because of this.

Emphasising the importance of this research is fundamental, and it majorly stems from the concern that drink spiking is at epidemic levels in the UK, with significant increases in the number of incidents being reported across the UK being found (Blandamer et al, 2023). It is an extremely prevalent modern-day issue, and many victims suffer from its harmful physical and psychological consequences (Metropolitan Police, 2024a), and they are also subjected to the unjust victim-blaming which follows. This strongly emphasises the national issue which women are repeatedly being urged to protect themselves from, particularly in spiking awareness posters, as demonstrated in this research. The covert use of drugs to spike, and therefore incapacitate, victims for the purpose of sexual assault is also a rising issue (Olszewski, 2009), with the harm caused to victims by violence against women and girls (VAWG) being immeasurable (NPCC, 2024b). VAWG includes any form of violence which is disproportionately carried out by men against women and girls (End Violence Against Women, 2022), which spiking has been proven to be, mirroring the gendered anxieties formed from women being the potential victims of (typically) male violence in the NTE (Vale Pires, 2024). This research urges that the

gendered expectations of women to prevent spiking must be eradicated and the responsibility should be shifted to the perpetrators of the crime, so that more efforts can be made to protect women and also support victims of spiking.

Methodologically, the CDA will be conducted through the utilisation of analysis tools which focus on specific elements of the collected posters. Further emphasising that CDA is issue-oriented, the discourses of responsabilisation will be prioritised and thoroughly unpacked using macro textual analysis, along with micro textual analysis which will focus on the presentation of the posters and the meaning behind the text and language of them (Ifversen, 2003). Modality analysis will also be a key method, looking at the realities and truths the posters present, and the language which expresses these factors (Simpson, 1993; Richardson, 2006). The combination of these analysis methods will present a picture of the extent to which women are responsabilised to prevent themselves from being spiked in the NTE in the posters, and the consequences of this. This will be crucial in highlighting how often women are instructed to act in a way which forces them to remain vigilant against the possibility of being spiked, when instead there should be more emphasis placed on looking to perpetrators and shifting the responsibility from potential victims.

The first main chapter of this dissertation is the literature review, which discusses the existing literature on the topic of spiking, in relation to women, and what previous research tells us about it. This chapter is a key part of the dissertation, providing a framework to relate its new findings to previous findings and literature on the research topic (Randolph, 2009). The literature review provides a clear understanding of why this research is important, identifying gaps in the existing literature, further highlighting its relevance. It contains three subsections; an overview of spiking, women and spiking, and responsabilisation, risk and gender studies – all of which possess relevance to the research topic and a balanced overview. The methodology chapter which follows contains an outline of how the research will be undertaken, providing clear explanations and justifications of the research strategy. With this research using a CDA approach, this chapter provides a section on the overview of this type of analysis, and how and why it is being used and its core principles, from the likes of authors such as van Dijk (2015) and Richardson (2006), demonstrating why this type of approach is best suited for the research. This CDA section is paired with an analysis strategy and selection strategy, which entail how the analysis is going to be done using CDA to unpack the choices and meanings behind the spiking awareness posters, paired with the justifications and rationale behind why this type of secondary research is being carried out. The third main chapter which closely follows is the analysis chapter, demonstrating the use of a CDA with micro textual, modality, and macro textual analysis methods to explore the various

elements of the posters. Looking at factors such as choice of colour and language, the truth modalities and the discourses of responsabilisation in the posters, this chapter aims to provide a clear picture of how women are responsabilised and pressured, as potential victims, to be their own forms of crime prevention in the social nighttime environment. The fifth and final chapter is a conclusion chapter, bringing the dissertation together and explaining the main conclusions of the research, as well as its implications and recommendations for future research and policy.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The act of spiking is one which is harmful and disturbing, involving the perpetrator giving a substance to another person through many different methods, mainly occurring in social settings, in the NTE (Olszewski, 2009). As proposed, the following research critically reviews the existing literature on several aspects of spiking, and explores the topic on a more profound level, breaking it down into all its forms and the crimes that contribute to it. Looking at the effects that spiking has on young women, including the extent to which women feel responsible for their own personal safety in protecting themselves, the research issues will be unpacked in relation to this.

This area of research carries great importance, because as spiking becomes an increasingly utilised crime, so does the disproportionality of women who are affected by it. As addressed and discussed thoroughly in the following research, with key themes of feminism and gender studies – it will look at the reasons behind the underreporting of the crime and the safety measures that women take against it which are integrated into their subconscious (Stanko, 2008). The lack of conceptualisation of spiking is also specifically acknowledged, which urgently needs to be improved moving forward in order to combat the management of crime prevention.

Theories including responsabilisation and risk society (Beck, 1992) will also be introduced in relation to the responsibilities of crime prevention that women must face within social environments where spiking poses a threat. In grasping an understanding of the causes and consequences of spiking and providing an awareness regarding its prevalence and severity; individuals, particularly women, should feel safer in social settings with a lack of fear of victimisation. Also, by emphasising the need for a shift of the main responsibility going from victims of the crime to the perpetrators, moving forward there should be greater clarity on how to combat the crime itself and the crime prevention strategies used towards it.

2.2 Overview of Spiking

The adding of substances, covertly, to another person with an absence of knowledge or consent from them is known as spiking (Burrell et al, 2023). These substances can be drugs or alcohol, and spiking can be its own action or can be carried out and followed by another offence, which is most commonly rape. There are multiple forms of spiking, drink spiking being the most common; but needle spiking,

vape or cigarette spiking and food spiking are all also utilised methods (Metropolitan Police, 2024b). Although there has been reports of drink spiking since the late 1900s (Campion-Vincent, 2022), with the date-rape drugs scare emerging in this period also (Donovan, 2016), a distinct offence for the crime is yet to be established, which would in turn allow an improvement in policing these instances. Across the public, there is a prevalent social agreement that the most significant risk of drug-facilitated sexual assault (DFSA), especially for young women, tends to come from proactive perpetrators, who covertly spike drinks in predominately social settings (Anderson et al, 2017). Normally using sedatives which are fast acting, such as Rohypnol or Gamma Hydroxybutyrate, these drugs can incapacitate victims and diminish their consciousness as well as any memories of the events that took place during their intoxication (Anderson et al, 2017). This causes concerns when it comes to prosecuting these offences due to the significant memory loss which victims suffer from, in turn disrupting their recollection of the night where the events of a spiking attack took place.

Acknowledging that more than half of all violent crime which takes place is known to be alcohol related (Flatley, 2016), the most central activity which takes place during the NTE is alcohol consumption (Hadfield et al, 2009). The NTE social environment influences progressive alcohol consumption, not only increasing peoples' levels of alcohol intoxication throughout the night but also making it easier for offenders to spike victims (Bellis et al, 2010; Moore et al, 2007). In research conducted by Haleem et al (2020) on violent crime in public space and the NTE in Manchester UK, violent crime was found to be the most rife on Saturday nights in certain public space hotspots, between the hours of 19:00 to 05:59. In relation to this, nightclubs attract offenders with the intention of spiking due to the sheer volume of people, the large venue and the distorting environment with a mix of flashing bright lights and loud music which sometimes results in noise-induced hearing loss (Johnson et al, 2014). Therefore, with nearly every individual in a venue consuming alcohol, it allows a perpetrator to be discreet and inconspicuous with their attacks on vulnerable victims, highlighting the consequent prevalence of the crime.

Although drink spiking has been, and still is, the most frequent method of spiking which is raised in multiple research reports and media sources (Bendau et al 2023; Donovan, 2016), spiking through injection with needles into the body is also emerging in reports, which is drawing substantial attention. An example of this is shown in a report from September 2021 to January 2022, where there were reports of 1,382 people who experienced injection spiking (Home Affairs Committee, 2022a). It is important, however, to reflect on the social stigmas that prevent victims from participating in surveys which address the issues of spiking and the deception of the crime. When observing this, these factors

reinforce the concerns that victims are disproportionately represented and, subsequently, the deep-rooted cycle of sexual crimes that result from spiking goes alarmingly undetected and underreported.

A lack of conceptualisation is evident when looking at spiking as a crime, as there is no single offence which wholly covers it – instead a range of more general offences which make it up are used to prosecute criminals. Spiking offences, which are covered by multiple laws, tend to be under the Offences Against the Person Act 1861 (Home Office, 2023), which covers any utilisation of harmful substances against victims. Cases where a victim is spiked by someone who sexually assaults them is covered by the Sexual Offences Act 2003 (Metropolitan Police, 2024b). As warned by the Home Affairs Committee (2022b), spiking remains an ‘invisible crime’ until more effort is made to improve awareness and support victims of the crime. This shows that there is a lack of available spiking data, which has increased difficulty of deriving a clear idea of the true extent of the crime; and it will continue to remain a prominent barrier to policing unless improvement of data collection is shown (Home Affairs Committee, 2022b), as well as an understanding of the data. The question of whether we should look at spiking as solely aiming for assault is a prominent one, and with many cases of it leading to sexual assault, it provides us with a clear picture that the violent act of spiking shows the intention of harm.

2.3 Women and Spiking

Following the new method of spiking through injection being labelled as a ‘Spiking Epidemic’ as perpetuated by media reports (Campion-Vincent, 2022), nightclub boycotts including a movement called ‘Girls Night In’ emerged (Gallagher, 2021; Nicholls, 2022) – which saw thousands of women across the UK stay at home instead of going on nights out. Coming from a feminist perspective – it seems that in awareness campaigns surrounding the consumption of alcohol in a public setting, women are unequally being given the responsibility of preventing a spiking attack and are being held personally accountable for their victimisation (Brooks, 2011a). Research by Sheard (2011) demonstrated that women have been told to restrict themselves to avoid victimisation, being given a range of different pieces of advice like ‘do not get drunk’, ‘do not wear revealing clothing’, and ‘do not be out at nighttime in certain areas’. These misogynistic viewpoints should be eradicated, and women should be given a voice and support, rather than having the blame placed onto them.

A study conducted by Davies et al (2024), showed that being a woman and recent clubbing experiences had been directly associated with recent spiking attacks. Gendered outcomes for individuals who have been subjected to spiking have also been indicated by previous research, with women normally suffering from more adverse side effects, like sexual assault and blacking out or sickness (Swan et al,

2017). Considering these factors, it provides us with a strong idea that women are the main targets for perpetrators to victimise when spiking. In addition to this, cultural indicators imply that being worried about having drinks spiked is an anxiety which is shared amongst young women, particularly university students, in the United Kingdom (Burgess et al, 2009). Not only do women worry about being spiked and feel a need to be on high alert whilst constantly checking their drinks whilst out with their friends, the fear of what could happen from being spiked also looms over them. This fear expressed by young women represents a modern depiction of the gendered fear of sexual violence (Brooks, 2014), working in harmony with the absurd general rape myth stating that 'women should look after themselves'.

A worldwide concern of sexual and gendered violence within the university field is prevalent, although it has been particularly marginalised specifically within UK research and policies (Phipps and Smith, 2012). In a study named 'Hidden Marks', the subsequent data suggested that British female students have an increased risk of being sexually victimised as compared with other groups in the population (Phipps and Smith, 2012). Although it is not specifically indicated in these research findings, we can infer that this risk is heightened by spiking attacks. It was also found that approximately 50% of respondents in the study stated that due to shame and embarrassment, they did not report a spiking incident (Phipps and Smith, 2012). This mirrors the negative impact that attitudes towards rape-support and victim-blaming have on people.

When looking at modern youth culture and university lifestyle, clubbing is a common activity which brings together the younger population. On nights out, women tend to have a shared consensus around safety in numbers, and generally 'stick together' as a form of vigilancy and safety, and to limit their risks of danger (and being spiked). These ideas identify gaps within the available literature and information on this topic, providing an opportunity to suggest that more research could be done to guide future recommendations on combatting the stigmas which women face in relation to protecting themselves against spiking. Women's internalised fear of crime is further reinforced by these factors and, given the fact that although nighttime policing and CCTV surveillance tend to be present during a night out (Brands et al, 2015), it is concerning that women still feel the need to be their own forms of crime prevention. Despite these efforts, perpetrators still manage to carry out attacks due to the subtlety of the crime, and data published by the National Police Chiefs' Council (2022), which was based on people who had reported being a victim of spiking, showed that women were the victims in a large majority of all spiking offences, at 74%.

It is also particularly important to note that women still receive the blame for being drink spiked, even when a perpetrator targets a woman in an attack and the individual does not have the capacity to

consent; in turn erasing perpetrators, and why they committed the crime, from the narrative (Ison et al, 2024). This is an alarming issue regarding victim-blaming, which in turn diminishes the severity of the crime. There is also a sense of uncertainty when it comes to understanding how women are targeted and identified by the perpetrator in spiking cases, presenting an identifiable gap in existing literature, however it has been established by many research studies that women are more likely to be attacked by a person they know (Brooks, 2009). This does not take away from the fact that many women are spiked by strangers, which happens much more often than people generally think, and this could be acknowledged and explored more in research. Whether women are spiked by someone known to them or a stranger, this still further adds to their fear of sexual violence, not because of specifically who could spike them, but through being fearful of the dangers of being spiked.

2.4 Responsibilisation, Risk and Gender Studies

The theory of risk society, as proposed by Beck (1992), is the concept of a social formation in which vulnerability to, and responsibility for, hazards are the object of calculation across populations; and the manner in which modern society is organised in response to risk. Given the modern patriarchal society in which we live in where the responsibility of crime prevention is being shifted across the general population, there is little effort being made as a community to reduce the risk of spiking, with victims still bearing much of the responsibility. Beck (1992) also speaks of 'reflexive modernisation' as a theory which led to a new age in which people must adapt to and accept the consequences of their own actions (Wimmer and Quandt, 2007). This is vital when looking at this theory from a viewpoint of spiking, ensuring that perpetrators are held responsible for the crimes they commit, rather than victims (particularly women) being blamed. It has been stated that all societies can be seen to be the solution to danger (Beck and Willms, 2014), however the willingness to support and protect potential victims from spiking is dependent upon holding perpetrators accountable and shifting the responsibility from women to protect themselves to the perpetrators.

The responsibility for crime prevention when it comes to spiking should never be placed onto potential victims, particularly women, and instead there is a need for more efforts to be made to take away a perpetrator's potential of orchestrating a spiking attack, like venue security carrying out rigorous search processes (Stephenson et al, 2023). The variety of safety strategies which are utilised by women, individually and in groups, emphasise how women presuming responsibility for their own safety is significantly integrated into their own consciousness (Brooks, 2011b). This means that there is an individual responsibility to stay vigilant as opposed to identifying drink spiking as a social or cultural problem. It is, unfortunately, not possible to dependably understand the extent of spiking in the UK,

due to many victims not reporting it for a number of reasons like humiliation, shame and memory loss – and this is why there is not a tremendous amount of official national statistics available (Marchioni, 2016). Although, a YouGov poll carried out in December 2022 identified that 10% of women said they had been spiked, with 5% of men saying they had been spiked (Home Office, 2023). It is acknowledged that both statistics are significantly concerning, however the stark contrast between the male and female statistics show not only the prevalence of spiking, but in particular the number of women who have experienced it, as compared to the lesser number of men. In harmony with this, the notion that women feel responsible for their individual victimisation because of their voluntary alcohol consumption before an incident creates a culture of self-responsibilisation.

Being in the NTE provokes a subconscious attitude in women, built to adapt to enjoying an alcohol-based environment whilst taking necessary precautions as if they are second nature. Although not directly in relation to the issue of spiking, research by Watts et al (2015) which explored young professional women's relationship with alcohol found them to be ashamed of and criticised for their drinking, which we can interpret as a link between the idea of responsabilisation and self-blaming when it comes to spiking and crimes of a sexual nature. Across contemporary Western societies, crime poses a threat which presents itself in people's everyday lives and has become a form of routine experience, intertwined with the idea that crime is normal and is a "routine part of modern consciousness... to be assessed and managed in much the same way that we deal with road traffic" (Garland, 1996, p. 446). Also in the words of Garland (1996, p. 453), the ongoing idea of responsabilisation is that "the state alone is not responsible for preventing and controlling crime". This notion that the responsibility for crime control should be, in theory, placed onto and shared by the general public puts tremendous amounts of pressure especially onto potential victims, particularly women, when it comes to spiking. Women should not be expected to accept the universal responsibility of crime control (Hinds and Grabosky, 2010), instead – we should be looking to the police in exercising their legitimate authority (Sunshine and Tyler, 2003) and using their strategies of crime prevention to predict and intercept further spiking attacks.

Although in the modern-day it is second nature to share the responsibility of crime prevention between venues like nightclubs, security staff and the police, the female obligation to protect themselves from spiking attacks could be argued to be the most utilised and reoccurring form of responsibility (Stevenson, 2018). This obligation extends to women's friends, whom they garner support from; assessing potential dangers and threats through proximity and closeness between themselves and others (males) – they adapt through panic. Traditional femininity also expects women to be engaging

in many safekeeping strategies (Campbell, 2005) which can affect their independent uses of public spaces like nightclubs in the NTE (Brooks, 2011a). The heavily gendered essence of the NTE presents women with, on one hand, an environment of freedom, but also a place of potential danger and victimisation (Stevenson, 2018). This is why women take on a range of personal and collective protective strategies in the hopes to manage any physical risks and gain a feeling of familiarity and safety (in numbers). The ongoing pressure to constantly remain attentive, and also employ safekeeping strategies, firstly diminishes a woman's freedom whilst individual responsabilisation to protect themselves is also expected, but they can also be exposed to significant blame if they are assumed to be making themselves vulnerable and not being vigilant enough (Nicholls, 2017). This further reiterates the belief that women should be taking responsibility for their personal safety on nights out, as predetermined by societal norms, which should be challenged in future research.

2.5 Conclusion

A reoccurring theme of ambiguity prevails throughout the various elements of spiking, which contributes to its pollution of the present era. A crime without a definitive framework can hardly be defined in the minds of women who have been sexually assaulted as a result of spiking, or perhaps a group of female friends deterred from their local nighttime social spaces (O'Brien et al, 2009). Consequently, an incomprehensible framework of spiking through its meaning allows the unjustified blaming of female victims, along with the suffering of its harmful repercussions. The universal truths of the female-targeted crime create mutual fear-based strategies, based on shared concerns of being a randomly targeted victim (Walklate, 2017). The atmosphere in which this crime thrives under leans in favour of the perpetrator through their utilisation of bustling crowds, an alcohol-centred environment and a manipulation of those who unknowingly disregard their vicinity (Bellis and Hughes, 2011), using all of these factors to their advantage.

As a direct effect of the dangers that spiking poses, increasing numbers of women are choosing to disengage with the NTE and its multiple businesses. Although many clubs are attempting to combat this epidemic as to not deter customers; through providing prevention methods and encouraging the awareness of the opportunities available for safety within the premises (Hughes and Bellis, 2003), this has proved to not be enough. Demand for change in this sector has been heard from both businesses and consumers alike. It has also been addressed by Prime Minister, Kier Starmer, "Reiterating his personal commitment to halve violence against women and girls, the Prime Minister will also confirm that his government will make spiking a new criminal offence" (UK Government, 2024, p. 1). A general shift in external attitudes and perceptions of the crime have allowed for more open conversation

regarding regulation and what can be done to overcome the issue of spiking. However, future literature should aim to assess the exposure of its discretionary traits, and what more can be done to remove the responsibility of crime prevention from women.

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1 Introduction

Crimes against women in the NTE, where drinking culture places such high value on sexual encounters, are prevalent and rising (Walker et al, 2023) with current statistics showing no decrease in incidents. For example, UN Women UK (2021) stated that 97% of 18-24 year old women reported that they had experienced some form of sexual harassment, and we can assume that a large proportion of these cases occurred in the NTE. As stated in the previous chapter, the latest generations have a newer example of violence against women, which is spiking, and as a student myself I have noticed much promotion on the awareness of this crime. This gave me the inspiration to conduct this research in the hopes to provide a better understanding of the crime and its discretion, and how women are responsabilised to protect themselves from violence committed by men. This responsabilisation of young women who engage in the NTE comes from having a duty forced upon them to ensure their own self-protection against potential risks, producing a higher fear of crime and a set of precautionary strategies instilled into them (Du Preez and Wadds, 2016) to try and reduce their chance of being spiked.

The topic of responsabilisation of women in the NTE is often spoken about amongst women as they are expected to be responsible agents (Lewis and McBride, 2024), which is a byproduct of advanced feminism, due to women having better communicative structures. These factors significantly stand out to me and have guided the following research, through collecting pictures of posters displayed in nightclubs and pubs which promote spiking awareness and analysing them using CDA. The discourse is evident but stagnant when assessing spiking, and through analysing these posters – while considering visual communication, which is rife within the current generation – my research challenges the idea that women should be responsible for looking after themselves on nights out.

3.2 Critical Discourse Analysis

In the words of van Dijk (2015, p. 466), “Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) is discourse analytical research that primarily studies the way social-power abuse and inequality are enacted, reproduced, legitimated, and resisted by text and talk in the social and political context”. This therefore means that CDA examines how both written and spoken language challenges social inequalities and power dynamics in society. The view of CDA is distinctive between language and society (Fairclough et al, 2011) and makes use of every relevant method of humanities and social sciences when studying important social problems presented in texts (van Dijk, 2015), such as gender inequality. Used by a significant number of scholars,

CDA involves a diverse set of concerns presenting themselves in several disciplines (Kress, 1990), such as the reproduction of sexism and racism through discourse. Further expressed by van Dijk (2011), when we look at CDA, power is conceptualised as control; for example, control of text or talk, or the structures of context, and, as a result of this variation, indirect control of people's minds. This is important to recognise, as the way in which relations of inequality and power reflect in many language forms (Blommaert and Bulcaen, 2000) is something which CDA investigates, to address societal problems and inequalities.

Through holding discourse in a view of social action, CDA also emphasises the intrinsic connection between language and social practice (Fairclough, 1995), with its model maintaining a focus on the investigation of the establishment of societal power relations and, resultantly, is reinforced using language. We can best see CDA as a "problem-oriented interdisciplinary research movement, subsuming a variety of approaches, each with different theoretical models, research methods and agenda" (Fairclough et al, 2011, p. 357), meaning that there is a mutual interest in many elements of changes in society, power and injustice. Due to CDA being a democratic approach which is highly context-sensitive and takes an ethical viewpoint on social issues (Huckin, 1997), it strives to improve society through acknowledging the relevant factors, textual and contextual, which give contribution to the interpretation of certain texts. These certain texts tend to be chosen when considering the consequences that they have on many people (Huckin, 1997). Further described by Fairclough (1995, p. 132), CDA is a form of discourse analysis which

"aims to systematically explore often opaque relationships of causality and determination between (a) discursive practices, events and texts, and (b) wider social and cultural structures, relations and processes; to investigate how such practices, events and texts arise out of and are ideologically shaped by relations of power and struggles over power".

Fairclough (1995) also cites Bourdieu (1977) in his work to support his suggestion that, with reference to opacity, the link between discourse, power and ideology can become unclear to people involved, and that general social practice is bound by unapparent causes and effects.

Emphasised by Wodak and Meyer (2016), CDA remains focused on how discourse enacts, confirms or challenges power abuse and inequality between social groups, which is a reoccurring principle throughout work published on CDA. Given that CDA takes an interest in the language-power relationship, CDA tends to specifically refer to the critical linguistic approach used by scholars to

discover the greater discursive unit of text to realistically be the basic communication unit (Wodak, 2002). Provided that this form of discourse analysis comes from a theory of language which is critical and sees language use as a type of social practice, CDA shows us that these social practices have a tie to certain historical contexts (Janks, 1997). They are also the means by which current social relations are reproduced and/ or contested and, as a result, different interests are served. Questions which pertain to the interests relate discourse to power relations (Janks, 1997), for example asking what the positioning of certain text is like and the effect this has on certain social groups.

The problems that have been acknowledged in relation to CDA research concern context, cognition and partiality (Tenorio, 2011). The theoretical foundations which built CDA can be tangled in many cases, with the use of certain concepts and categories being inconsistent, thus presenting a lack of encouragement of the production of a systematic theory (Tenorio, 2011). Without opposing the cause of CDA, Widdowson (2004) also presents doubts on CDA's modes of analysis, pointing out that there is a gap between the meaning of the addresser and the interpretation of said meaning by the addressee. This is on the grounds that "the perlocutionary effect is not a feature of texts but a function of discourse, in which the addressee's assumptions are shaped by their knowledge and beliefs", according to Tenorio (2011, p. 195) who commented on Widdowson's (2004) critiques. However, since CDA has developed into an established methodological approach and is a rapidly developing field (Bloor and Bloor, 2007), it still has many merits attached to it. CDA is concerned with seeking out where social problems originate from, whilst analysing them productively (Bloor and Bloor, 2007), looking at texts in terms of their wider social and political significance. This acts as a tool for the social construction of reality, as well as an apparatus of power and ideological control (Fernández Martínez, 2007), giving its analysis methods strong credit to provide explanations for social and power issues. These issues can therefore be clearly addressed and challenged, giving ample opportunity for discussions around injustices and prejudices presented in texts.

3.3 Selection Strategy

When considering my selection strategy, it was concluded that the best way to conduct my research would be to carry out a secondary study with the collection of qualitative artifacts which I would then analyse using CDA. Secondary data is known as data which has been collected by someone else but can be used as the main source for research, or as a supplement for the data which is collected (Adams et al, 2014). Given the nature of my research problem and the issue being addressed, which involves the exploration of the responsabilisation of women when looking at spiking as a crime, I decided that secondary research was the best option as opposed to primary research. Primary data is most

commonly collected through surveys and interviews (O'Leary, 2021), which would not coincide with the sensitive nature of my research, for example if it was conducted by interviewing victims of spiking or women who were fearful of spiking. This would have allowed space for many ethical issues to arise, and formal approval which would have been required by my university institution would have been difficult to obtain (Howitt and Cramer, 2017). This therefore demonstrates that secondary research is the most well-suited to my project, as it does not involve any at-risk participants, like primary research would (O'Leary, 2021), and my use of CDA to analyse spiking awareness posters can still address the issues of women being responsabilised and used as strategies towards spiking prevention.

Further consideration of the type of secondary data which I would be collecting took place when designing my methodology. After weighing up which type of data would be the best to use in my research, with secondary data including data which is examined to address key social issues (Vartanian, 2011), I decided to collect pictures of posters displayed in venues in the NTE, like pubs and nightclubs (Roberts, 2006), in order to provide a real-life depiction of how women are responsabilised in posters on spiking awareness. The posters which I selected varied in text, imagery and colours, however a common theme prevailed throughout the majority of the posters: the responsabilisation of women. When considering how and why I took the pictures of each poster, I had a specific criteria in mind when looking at them. For example, in certain venues I visited, some posters were on the first wall I saw, which was important as they caught my attention straight away, meaning that this would be the same for the general public upon entry. Another common place where posters were displayed was in the women's toilets, showing the awareness that women are often the victims of spiking. I also considered the way in which the posters were presented, trying to focus on the most impactful and eye-catching posters, looking at factors like the language used, as well as text size and colours. Some posters I decided not to picture, due to them not clearly being centred around spiking awareness or targeted towards women – and I therefore deemed them as not relevant in contributing to my research.

The secondary sources used in this research can justify the research purpose without using a primary data approach, with many valuable insights being gained into topics and discussions which emerge from looking at the data which is gathered (Choy, 2014). This is a notable strength of doing CDA as there will be a valuable outcome of this research, with the focus on spiking as an ongoing issue being put into perspective and an emphasis is being placed on a change needing to happen, without invasive questions. Using the posters I collated, I also carried out a pilot study, which is a small-scale study which mirrors the main study but in a smaller size (Van Teijlingen and Hundley, 2001). I did this by picking out five of the posters I pictured and analysed them using annotations whilst answering a pre-prepared set

of questions I created when looking at the posters, considering the way in which they were designed and the effects that this had on potential readers. This significantly helped my work as it gave me an insight into how my main analysis would look, and if there was anything I could do differently when it came to using CDA.

3.4 Analysis Strategy

For my analysis strategy, much of my influence in choosing to use CDA came from the likes of Fairclough (2001), Wodak (2014), and van Dijk (1993). One author in particular whose work had a significant influence on my choice of analysis was Richardson (2006), who talks about lexical analysis as the choice of meaning and words. The analysis of particular words used in a text is nearly always the first stage of any discourse analysis (Richardson, 2006), and this is something which I began to think about when I started to closely examine the posters I pictured on spiking awareness. With one of the first questions which came to mind being 'how is the text on the poster being presented and what were the implications of this on the reader's experience?', this led me to begin considering how the words reinforced and reproduced the imprint of social groups and particularly of value judgements, as words convey connoted and denoted meanings (Richardson, 2006). Later on, this question and many others were used in my pilot study – to analyse the posters in a way which engaged with critical questions to extract and challenge the discourses framed within each poster. Through the analysis of gender stereotypes, posters differentiated in design and presentation, with feminised factors, such as colour, font and graphic design used to further enhance the responsabilisation of women for preventing spiking. This contrasts the alternative design of the male oriented posters, using a threatening nature to assert authority and candidly portray the consequences of offending using spiking. These factors will be assessed in my analysis chapter, as they contribute heavily to the constructs of responsibility and societal boundaries in which this crime operates.

Sentence construction, known as modality, is also something which interested me when reading Richardson's (2006) work, and he cited Simpson's (1993, p. 47) definition, "modality refers broadly to a speaker's attitude towards, or opinion about, the truth of a proposition expressed by a sentence". This is particularly compelling, as modalities tend to be indicated through the use of certain language (Richardson, 2006), such as words like 'you', 'your', and 'their', which were seen in the posters, representing certain tropes such as responsibility tropes and 'how to' tropes. Defined by Corbett (1990, p. 426), a trope is "a deviation from the ordinary and principal signification of a word, meaning a trope takes words and uses them to denote-connote something which is other than their ordinary meaning" – such as used for the presentation of truth or reality. Referring back to the pilot study I conducted and

the questions I created, this allowed me to become more knowledgeable about how CDA is used and how I could use it to sufficiently analyse the posters. I looked at the way in which the text in the posters spoke to the reader, for example if it was telling them to do something, whether it was aimed at perpetrators or victims of spiking, and how the text was positioned and the meaning behind this. All types of words carry meanings (Richardson, 2006), and by carrying out this pilot study, it allowed me to look at the meanings behind each and every word used in my collected data. Through the use of CDA, I analysed my posters in the same approach used in the pilot study through looking at the way the text is presented, the use of language, the use of imagery, and who the posters are aimed at. This allowed me to draw conclusions and provide an understanding on the extent to which women are responsabilised in relation to spiking.

3.5 Conclusion

Through my previously mentioned pilot study and data collection of spiking awareness posters, this secondary research allowed me to draw conclusions on how women are responsabilised when we look at spiking, and the gendered stereotypes which can be seen in my collected research, which will be fully unpacked in my analysis chapter. Using CDA, I drew upon the language, text and colours used in these posters and the deeper meanings behind these elements to provide distinctive findings around how women are responsabilised for spiking prevention.

Chapter 4: Analysis

4.1 Introduction

Through carrying out a CDA of the collected spiking awareness posters, comprising of the use of micro textual analysis, modality analysis, and macro analysis, this chapter provides a comprehensive exploration of how women are responsabilised to protect themselves from spiking in the NTE. Specific dimensions such as colour, font, language and the discourses of responsabilisation in the posters were analysed, using a feminist perspective to emphasise the gender-imbalanced responsabilisation across these posters. This mirrored the general consensus that women are more likely to be burdened with the responsibility of spiking prevention (Dresler and Anderson, 2018). Through focusing on women within the discourse, this analysis used these aspects of the posters to provide a further explanation of how women feel the pressure to behave accordingly to the information being presented to them in posters displayed in the NTE. As women are being held responsible, as a group, for their own safety and for the prevention of spiking attacks, the implications of this were also inferred in the analysis to show the harmful consequences of potential victims being responsabilised to prevent spiking, rather than the responsibility being placed onto perpetrators.

4.2 Micro Textual Analysis

The first analysis method used to assess the posters was micro textual analysis, which looked at the choice of the presentation used in the posters I collected for my research, and how these choices consequently responsabilised women. Micro textual analysis looks at the choice of presentation, phrases, structure and the layout of texts – and where micro-level approaches are used, the role and meaning of the text holds great importance (Ifversen, 2003). Therefore, using this type of analysis allowed for the opportunity to look at deeper meanings of text and presentations, and provide explanations for the issues which were being addressed in this research which has an issue-oriented nature.

When considering the commonalities between the colour schemes used in the posters I collected for my research, it was evident that the use of the colour ‘pink’ was a prominent reoccurring factor in the spiking awareness campaigns. Whether it was used as a background colour, or text colour, it was an overriding element of the posters, used to encapsulate the female essence, and encourage women to notice and read them. This was seen in the following examples:

Fig 1 & 2. Images showing 'Poster 8' and Poster 10

The utilisation of the colour 'pink', which is most associated with the feminine aesthetic (Atkinson et al, 2024), was tactically used by the designers of these posters to specifically attract the attention of women in the NTE, used as a strategy to draw in the target audience (women) to read the posters and be aware of this present day issue known as spiking. Posters like the ones shown above have been made to be more appealing to women and given that 'pink' is a colour which is more stereotypically associated with women rather than men (LoBue and DeLoache, 2011), women are more likely to read this type of poster as they resonate with the femininity which presents itself in them. This, in turn, contributed to the responsabilisation of women in being crime prevention tools against spiking in the NTE, and it has been indicated that this female obligation is argued to be the most ongoing presented responsibility (Stevenson, 2018). This made me challenge whether the motivation behind these posters was not just to support the female community, but to responsabilise them to make them believe that they need to be on high alert to prevent spiking attacks, rather than looking to perpetrators holding the main responsibility of the crime.

Using a more specific example, the design and presentation of the following poster was also closely analysed and established further evidence of the responsabilisation of women:

Fig 3. Image to show 'Poster 11'

Given that this poster was displayed in the venue's women's toilets, it was already established that women were the target audience when it was designed. The text in all capital letters, along with the language used in the poster being blunt and straight to the point whilst providing specific instructions to women on what to do in the NTE regarding shielding their drinks – these factors forced a sense of pressure upon women to be constantly vigilant and remain on high alert. For example, the language like 'keep a close eye' and 'never leave them unattended' were considered to be forceful forms of telling women what to do, with emphasis placed on protecting their drinks. The pressure this language presented reflected an element of responsabilisation – through telling women how to behave and that they should be assuming responsibility for their own safety – rather than addressing other crime prevention methods, like bar staff providing cup covers to customers buying alcoholic drinks in the NTE. This seemed as though space is then left for people to victim-blame, given that if a victim was to be spiked, and the responsibility had already been placed onto them, the belief that it was most likely their own fault becomes further emphasised, due to the shared consensus by many people that women should look after themselves (Sheard, 2011). The use of imagery in this poster was also considered, with a human hand holding what seemed to be a spiking-drug over a drink which was inferred to be alcoholic – this looked to be a very realistic depiction of what spiking can look like. The poster design could have used this as a scare factor, showing women what spiking could look like, and causing them to consider what could happen to them if they do not remain vigilant. The use of black and white imagery, rather than colour, however, was considered to be less noticeable, given that posters with colour usually attract a reader's attention much more than a black and white poster, due to colour coordination seeming more appealing (Keegan and Bannister, 2003), therefore meaning that this poster may not be as effective in reaching women, the target audience, as others.

It was clear to see that the words of instructions on the posters, along with certain use of imagery and language, played a big role in responsabilising women, with the purpose of these posters being to make

women aware of potential spiking attacks and how to prevent them. The overall purpose of these posters which was established was for women to feel obliged to take responsibility for their safety, potentially hindering their enjoyment of socialising and engaging with the NTE. This forced responsibility upon women further reinforced the belief that women should look after and protect themselves from spiking, contributing to women's fear of sexual violence (Brooks, 2014), being given no reassurance that perpetrators hold the main responsibility, not potential victims.

4.3 Modality Analysis

'Modality' is a term used to describe sentence construction (Richardson, 2006), and as it refers to a speaker's attitudes or opinions about the truth of a proposition which is expressed by a sentence (Simpson, 1993). It is all about the perception of a reality and a truth (Richardson, 2006), and this section focused on the truth in action which the posters presented. In order to analyse the ways in which language expressed relationships to reality or truth in this case, the analysis looked at the words which the posters used to address the reader, and how this consequently responsabilised women. Also drawing upon the wider logic of responsabilising, this was used to negotiate why choices were made about forms of presentation and modalities in the posters.

Readers being addressed as a group, being told what to do and how to act in a spiking prevention scenario in the NTE was a common theme which prevailed throughout the collected spiking awareness posters. Women being told through the posters to behave in a certain way to protect themselves, and others, from being spiked would instil a fear in them of what could happen if these instructions being presented were not followed. It was already known that young women's fear of drink spiking resulted from the gendered fear of sexual violence, which came from being in the sexualised environment of the NTE (Brooks, 2014). The combination of this and having a forced responsibility upon them to act with a sense of self-preservation to protect themselves from harm (being spiked) comes from being told how to act in a social nighttime environment, by people and by spiking awareness posters, which was shown in this analysis. This presented itself through the language used in many of the posters, which was worded in a way which directly spoke to readers and told them to look out for certain signs of spiking, how to detect if someone had been spiked, and how to act as a result of being spiked or knowing someone who had been spiked. These truth modalities were, in essence, presented by the grouping of women, who were being addressed through the use of language like 'you', 'your', and 'their'. This represented the responsabilisation of women through the clear pressure in the posters to act accordingly to the presented information, which would contribute to women's fear of spiking and the

consequences which follow. As a result, women become a form of crime prevention, through following the strict set of instructions presented to them in these posters.

The following example mirrored this:

Fig 4. Image to show 'Poster 7'

With a focus on the 'what to do' section of this poster, it provided a set of instructions to readers on what 'you' should do if 'you' or someone 'you' know has been spiked. Although this was seen to be somewhat helpful as it could be used as a guide by people who had never experienced or witnessed spiking before, in truth, it was specifically telling women, who are proven to be more likely to be victims of spiking (Stephenson et al, 2023), to take responsibility for their safety in a spiking prevention scenario. Through the use of the word 'you', it specifically urged readers to respond to the set of instructions which were shown, with the disregard of acknowledgement that women should not be solely responsible for crime prevention, instead the responsibility should have been focused on potential perpetrators and other forms of crime prevention, like security staff. When this poster was directly telling potential victims and witnesses that they should respond in a certain way; for example, they must 'alert the venue', they may not be in a position to do this, which was not acknowledged. The concerning reality here was that the responsibility was solely on women to look after themselves and prevent spiking, as well as deal with the aftermath if they experienced it. This could create an unhealthy space for victims to feel that it was their fault if they were spiked and makes them question whether they could have prevented the crime from happening, due to the truth that they had been harshly responsabilised in these posters.

Further truth modalities were identified in the following leaflet:

Fig 5, 6 & 7. Images to show 'Poster 12c'

Rather than this leaflet remaining focused on potential perpetrators, with the acknowledgement that spiking is illegal and punishable by law, the truth that presented itself was the overriding element of the responsabilisation of women. A commonality between the posters, which was shown in this leaflet is a section telling the reader 'how to help' if 'you' think a friend has had 'their' drink spiked. The use of these pronouns showed the group mentality which this leaflet represented, by addressing women as a group who should know what to do in a spiking scenario. Given that female friends carve out spaces of safety and familiarity in the gendered NTE (Stevenson, 2018), the designers of these posters most likely used this knowledge to their advantage to responsabilise women in addressing them and their friends,

knowing that they would feel obliged to make the conscious effort to protect themselves, and each other, from potential danger. The 'how to' tropes which present themselves in the posters reflected the truth that the strategic creation of the posters was used to look as though they were helping through giving instructions, when, in reality, they were used in order to target women to follow strict rules and look out for their individual, and group, safety. This most likely created an individual responsibility women instantly took on, without realising it was wrong and unjust for them to carry the full responsibility of crime prevention in a potential spiking scenario.

4.4 Macro Textual Analysis

Using macro textual analysis to analyse the posters as a whole, looking at their overall purpose and main theme from a broader perspective (van Dijk, 2007), this section of the chapter focused on the discourses of responsabilisation of women in preventing spiking attacks. Given that responsabilisation was the main theme which reoccurred throughout many of the spiking awareness posters, there was much to be said about its discourses and the challenges which women face in preventing spiking. Whilst assessing potential risks and avoiding spiking, and subsequently sexual assault (Tokle et al, 2023), these individual responsibilities which women feel that they must adopt, to prevent themselves from becoming victims, come from societal expectations to protect themselves against the perpetrators of these crimes.

One of the key discourses of responsabilisation which was identified was prevention strategies, which was seen in the following posters:

Fig 8 & 9. Images to show 'Poster 5' and 'Poster 13'

The 'Ask for Angela' concept was one which could be seen to be helpful for women to use to escape uncomfortable situations and seek safety, however it required women to seek the help/ support being presented to them, which still possessed the element of the responsibility being placed onto them, which was a concerning issue – particularly if a victim had already been spiked and was not in a conscious state to utilise this strategy. The posters were telling women to 'Ask for Angela', which was still telling them what to do and therefore responsabilising them to look out for their safety, rather than identifying that perpetrators were the issue which should be looked out for. It is also important to acknowledge that it might be too late for women to use this strategy if they had already fallen victim to spiking, and the requirement for women to read this poster and act on it is situational, given that victims may not have had the chance to read it before being attacked. Another significant prevention strategy which women were being told to use is to 'monitor their drinks' (Burgess et al, 2009), which was seen in Poster 11.

This notion that women should be watching their drinks constantly, diminishing their enjoyment of being out in the NTE, was an identified safekeeping strategy which women feel huge pressure to use when engaging with the NTE (Campbell, 2005). This not only provides people with an excuse to victim-blame if a woman is spiked, but it may also cause victims to blame themselves due to being under such strict protocol to cover their drinks whilst in a social environment (Duff et al, 2005). The advice to 'stay in groups' and 'avoid potentially dangerous environments' also responsabilised women to restrict themselves and behave in a certain way to prevent potential danger, which further oppressed women and their ability to enjoy an alcohol-centred environment – due to feeling the need to remain vigilant at all times and be on high alert for potential perpetrators and spiking attacks.

Linking to the idea of individual, and group, prevention strategies, another evident discourse of responsabilisation was women being assumed to be the supervisors of their own safety. The ongoing force of women being told to take charge of their own safety and well-being comes at a price – the amplification of women's fear of sexual violence (Brooks, 2014). Women's free will, to dress and behave how they like, becomes lessened when they are told how to behave and interact with others through the posters (Sheard, 2011) – in order to prevent spiking. This further amplified the gendered expectations of women, given that men would not be told how to act and dress in order to prevent themselves from being spiked (Nicholls, 2015). The pressure on women to conform to societal norms which tell them how to carry themselves to avoid being spiked is a pressure which they face significantly

more than men do (Nicholls, 2015), demonstrating the gender disparity between women and men in the NTE.

Following on from this, it was clearly seen that the discourses of responsabilisation in the context of the posters were deeply gendered, with women being encouraged to instil precautionary measures against spiking into their night-out routine (Stanko, 2008), whilst these strategies were not expected by men. Men do not suffer from the pressure to protect themselves against spiking and sexual violence in the same way women do, which demonstrated the unequal burden which is placed onto women (Brooks, 2009), who are being repeatedly responsabilised to try their hardest to prevent themselves from being spiked. All these discourses held the shared ignorance of perpetrators, not acknowledging that spiking tends to be committed by perpetrators who carry malicious intent (Burrell et al, 2023). Instead, they focused on women being their own form of crime prevention and monitoring their every move, whilst always making efforts to remain vigilant and on high alert at all times.

Although some of the posters looked like this:

Fig 10. Images to show 'Poster 7'

As with poster 9, the acknowledgement that 'spiking is a crime' did not necessarily give the impression that they would deter perpetrators from committing the crime, given that they still contained the element of responsabilising women in a spiking scenario much more than perpetrators. Given that the discourses of responsabilisation presented themselves throughout the posters, the bottom line which

was established was that women should always be aware of spiking and protect themselves from it, because no one else will.

4.5 Conclusion

Using the various forms of analysis to carry out a CDA looking at the responsabilisation of women in the collected posters on spiking awareness, a range of conclusions were made on how the presentations in the posters responsabilised women, and the implications which could follow. The analysis was carried out to identify and explore the issue of women being responsabilised in the NTE to prevent themselves from becoming victims of spiking, and this was very apparent upon analysing. Focusing on the key elements of the posters, like the feminisation of them through the use of the colour 'pink' to draw women's attention, and the direct and authoritative language to create a sense of panic and fear, these aspects, along with many others, were utilised in the poster designs to responsabilise women. The tropes and modalities, which presented themselves throughout the posters, showed a clear picture of how women are forced to protect themselves from spiking, with men seen to not be suffering from this burden. More emphasis should be placed on preventing future victim-blaming and the moral implications women face when they have such a great deal of expectations forced upon them to protect themselves in a spiking prevention scenario, with the gendered stereotypes needing to shift so that the safety of potential victims of this crime is not just dependant on how well women protect themselves.

Chapter 5: Conclusion

This dissertation has provided many valuable insights into the proposed research issues, exploring the extent to which women bear the responsibility of crime prevention in relation to spiking. Drawing upon previous literature to lay the groundwork on how women experience the NTE and how responsible they feel for looking after and protecting themselves from spiking, this allowed for the proposed research to look closely into spiking awareness posters and how they responsabilise women to protect themselves. One of the main conclusions found is that the posters were designed to specifically speak to women, as a target group, through the use of certain colours and language which draw in women to read the provided information. This clearly demonstrated that women were much more the audience who the poster designers were aiming to responsabilise, in order to make them feel backed into a corner and have no other choice but to behave how they are being told to. This mirrors the gendered stereotypes which state that 'women should look after and protect themselves', which is found to be much more reoccurring than men being told what to do. The CDA of the collected posters uncovered alarming truths surrounding the information presented to women in the posters, and the way in which it is designed to speak to women in an authoritative way to make them feel threatened and fear the consequences of what could happen if they do not remain vigilant against potential spiking attacks. These methods used in the posters force women to act accordingly and prevent spiking attacks, but as a result allow more space to victim-blame if they do become victims of a spiking attack. These conclusions are vital in addressing the discourses of responsabilisation in the presented posters, which look to women to be human forms of crime prevention and force them to feel solely responsible for their safety in the NTE. The analysis in this research, which was carried out to call out these unjust views of potential victims needing to protect themselves from spiking, demonstrates that there is a need for change in spiking awareness campaigns and posters, and that perpetrators should be looked at more closely so that we can combat the issue of spiking, rather than potential victims bearing the entire responsibility.

Given that CDA is primarily interested in the understanding of pressing social issues (van Dijk, 2006), although my research aimed to do this, it may not capture the full extent of the issue of spiking and how women, globally, do truly feel the responsibility of their safety through looking at the presented posters, and many other sources of information. It is important to note, however, that my analysis provides clarity and recognition of the harmful consequences of women having responsibility, and blame, put onto them in certain scenarios where spiking could occur. This research could also be

expanded with a more varied set of data, for example looking at more venues in the NTE, where spiking awareness posters are presented to the public. The posters which were collected were specifically in two locations: Greater Manchester and Leeds. In order to gain an even more accurate picture of how women are responsabilised, nationally, to protect themselves from being spiked, more locations could be visited to collect a more widespread set of data and allow for an analysis involving a wider range of posters.

Considering how this research can support recommendations for future exploration on this topic, it is worth noting that it provides a gateway for future studies through looking at the consequences of how women suffer from the responsibility of spiking prevention being forced upon them. It considers how spiking awareness/ prevention posters tell women what to do in a way which unwillingly forces responsibility upon them with no room for other factors, like awareness of suspicious activity by perpetrators, being considered, and a huge disregard of perpetrators who commit the spiking offence and cause the harm towards victims. The recognised instilled fear of spiking in women is notably seen as a result of this responsabilisation which presented itself in the collected posters for this research and provides strong foundations for future research to further explore this serious issue. Following on from this dissertation, a recommendation for future research would be to look more closely at how women truly feel about the burden of crime prevention in spiking scenarios, and the role this plays in hindering their enjoyment in the NTE. The analysis from this research looks at how the posters responsabilise women in spiking prevention, and infers how this would make them feel, however future research could possibly look at interviewing women in relation to this, to take it a step further and capture the full extent on how women view this issue and how it affects them. This would allow for further expansion on the issues which have been addressed in this research, providing a broader explanation on women's feelings toward this recognised burden of spiking prevention.

It is important to acknowledge that the key recommendation for policy from this research, which emphasises the need for spiking to be specifically labelled as a criminal offence rather than it being made up by multiple offences, is to be implemented as part of the 'Crime and Policing Bill' this year (Ministry of Justice, 2025). The Bill uses modern language which covers incidents of spiking and creates a new administering a harmful substance offence, which will carry a possible 10-year prison sentence (Phillips, 2025). This essential policy change is a positive advancement, with the new classification making it easier for victims to report if they have been spiked due to the clarity provided in the new Bill (Phillips, 2025). In relation to this breakthrough, a £250,000 government-funded scheme has been started which will entail teaching staff how to detect the warning signs of spiking crimes, and it is aiming

to train 10,000 members of staff across pubs, clubs and bars for free (Philips, 2025). These significant changes in the law and nationwide training programme are vital in combatting spiking and holding perpetrators accountable, with victims feeling more supported and the responsibility being, rightly, placed onto perpetrators – giving women the freedom to enjoy themselves and freeing them of the relentless obligation of spiking prevention. With these visible efforts being made to reduce spiking attacks and target perpetrators, women, as a result, will be less responsabilised in real life spiking scenarios and, hopefully, in future spiking awareness campaigns.

References

Adams, J., Khan, H.T.A. and Raeside, R. (2014) *Research methods for business and social science students*. 2nd ed. London: SAGE.

Anderson, L.J., Flynn, A. and Pilgrim, J.L. (2017) A global epidemiological perspective on the toxicology of drug-facilitated sexual assault: A systematic review. *Journal of Forensic and Legal Medicine*, 47, pp. 46-54.

Atkinson, A., Meadows, B. and Sumnall, H. (2024) 'Just a colour?': Exploring women's relationship with pink alcohol brand marketing within their feminine identity making. *International Journal of Drug Policy*. [Online]. 125, p. 104337. Available from <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugpo.2024.104337>> [Accessed 26.03.2025].

Beck, U. (1992) *Risk Society: Towards a New Modernity*. London: SAGE Publications Ltd.

Beck, U. and Willms, J. (2014) *Conversations with Ulrich Beck*. Germany: Polity Press.

Bellis, M. A., Hughes, K., Quigg, Z., Morleo, M., Jarman, I. and Lisboa, P. (2010) Cross-sectional measures and modelled estimates of blood alcohol levels in UK nightlife and their relationships with drinking behaviours and observed signs of inebriation. *Substance Abuse Treatment, Prevention, and Policy*. [Online]. 5 (1), p. 5. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1186/1747-597X-5-5>> [Accessed 01.11.2024].

Bellis, M.A. and Hughes, K. (2011) Getting drunk safely? Night-life policy in the UK and its public health consequences. *Drug and alcohol review*, 30 (5), pp. 536-545.

Bendau, A., Michnevich, T., Petzold, M.B., Piest, A., Schmolke, R., Jakobson, D., Ahrend, K., Reitz, T., Roediger, L. and Betzler, F., (2023) Spiking versus speculation? Perceived prevalence, probability, and fear of drink and needle spiking. *Journal of Drug Issues*. [Online]. 55 (1), pp. 89-103. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/00220426231197826>> [Accessed 14.11. 2024].

Blandamer, T., Daniels, J., Dear, J., Birse, F., Carlton, E., Burgess, K. and Roberts, T. (2023) Drink and injection spiking: how to approach an increase in presentations? *Emergency Medicine Journal*, 40 (4), pp. 308-312.

Blommaert, J. and Bulcaen, C. (2000) Critical discourse analysis. *Annual review of Anthropology*, 29 (1), pp. 447-466.

Bloor, M. and Bloor, T. (2007) *The Practice of Critical Discourse Analysis: An Introduction*. [Online]. London: Routledge. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203775660>> [Accessed 25.02.2025].

Bourdieu, P. (1997) *Outline of a Theory of Practice*. Cambridge: CUP.

Brands, J., Aalst, I.V. and Schwanen, T. (2015) Safety, surveillance and policing in the night-time economy: (Re)turning to numbers. *Geoforum*, (62), pp. 24-37.

Brooks, O. (2009) *Negotiating Power, Resistance and Control: Young Women's Safety in Bars, Pubs and Clubs*. Degree thesis, University of Sterling.

Brooks, O. (2011a) 'Guys! Stop Doing It!': Young Women's Adoption and Rejection of Safety Advice When Socializing in Bars, Pubs and Clubs. *British Journal of Criminology*. [Online]. 51 (4), pp. 635–651. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1093/bjc/azr011>> [Accessed 15.11.2024].

Brooks, O. (2011b) Consuming Alcohol in Bars, Pubs and Clubs: A risky freedom for young women? *Annals of Leisure Research*. [Online]. 11 (3-4), pp. 331-350. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1080/11745398.2008.9686801>> [Accessed 24.11.2024].

Brooks, O. (2014) Interpreting Young Women's Accounts of Drink Spiking: The Need for a Gendered Understanding of the Fear and Reality of Sexual Violence. *Sociology*, 48 (2), pp. 300-316.

Burgess, A., Donovan, P. and Moore, S.E.H. (2009) Embodying Uncertainty? Understanding Heightened Risk Perception of Drink 'Spiking'. *The British Journal of Criminology*. [Online]. 49 (6), pp. 848-862. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1093/bjc/azp049>> [Accessed 15.11.2024].

Burrell, A., Woodhams, J., Gregory, P. and Robinson, E. (2023) *Spiking: Prevalence and Motivation*. [Online]. University of Birmingham: The Institute for Global Innovation. Available from: <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Amy-Burrell/publication/373895390_Spiking_Prevalence_and_Motivation/links/6501dadd9763a22fa3df74e0/Spiking-Prevalence-and-Motivation.pdf> [Accessed 31.10.2024].

Campbell, A. (2005) Keeping the 'Lady' Safe: The Regulation of Femininity through Crime Prevention Literature. *Critical Criminology*. 13 (2), pp. 119-140.

Campion-Vincent, V. (2022) From stories to behaviour, the ebb and flow of fears and panics: Discussion of the needle-spiking epidemic scares of 2021–2022. *Literatura Ludowa. Journal of Folklore and Popular Culture*, 66 (3), pp. 71-91. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.12775/LL.3.2022.004>> [Accessed 15.11.2024].

Choy, L.T. (2014) The Strengths and Weaknesses of Research Methodology: Comparison and Complimentary between Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches. *IOSR journal of humanities and social science*, 19 (4), pp. 99-104.

Corbett, E.P.J. (1990) *Classical Rhetoric for the Modern Student*. Oxford University Press.

Davies, E.L., Piatkowski, T., Frankovitch, A., Puljević, C., Barratt, M.J., Ferris, J.A. and Winstock, A.R. (2024) Exploring Experiences of Drink and Needle Spiking Incidents Among Global Drug Survey Respondents from 22 Countries. *Journal of Drug Issues*. [Online]. 0 (0). Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/00220426241248613>> [Accessed 15.11.2024].

Donovan, P. (2016) *Drink spiking and predatory drugging: A modern history*. Springer. Bloomsburg: Palgrave Macmillan New York.

Dresler, E. and Anderson, M. (2018) Drinking to the “edge”: gender differences in context-specific risks. *Health education*, 118 (1), pp. 17-30.

Du Preez, L. and Wadds, P. (2016) Gendered responsabilisation in the night-time economy. In: *Refereed Proceedings of TASA 2016 Conference*, p. 62.

Duff, C., Dearle, L. and Bradonjic, Z. (2005) *Evaluation of the Crime Prevention Victoria/Convenience Advertising 2004 Victorian Drink Spiking Community Education Campaign*. [Online]. Available from: <<https://cms.convenienceadvertising.com.au/assets/7079c7ed-9f09-44a8-ae69-8cdcf2db8c66.pdf>> [Accessed 06.04.2025].

End Violence Against Women (2022) *BREAKING DOWN VIOLENCE AGAINST WOMEN*. [Online]. Available from: <<https://www.endviolenceagainstwomen.org.uk/explainer/>> [Accessed 06.04.2025].

Fairclough, N. (1995) *Critical Discourse Analysis: The Critical Study of Language*. London: Routledge.

Fairclough, N. (2001) Critical discourse analysis as a method in social scientific research. *Methods of critical discourse analysis*, 5 (11), pp. 121-138.

Fairclough, N., Mulderrig, J. and Wodak, R. (2011) Critical Discourse Analysis. In: van Dijk, T.A. ed. *Discourse studies: a multidisciplinary introduction*. Thousand Oaks, California: Sage Publications, pp. 357-378.

Fernández Martínez, D. (2007) From Theory to Method: A methodological approach within critical discourse analysis. *Critical Discourse Studies*. [Online]. 4 (2), pp. 125-140. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1080/17405900701464790>> [Accessed 25.02.2025].

Flatley, J. (2016) *Crime statistics, focus on violent crime and sexual offences, 2013/14*. Office for National Statistics. [Online]. Available from: <<https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/crimeandjustice/compendium/focusonviolentcrimeandsexualoffences/2015-02-12>> [Accessed 15.11.2024].

Gallagher S. (2021) *Girls night in: 'Spiking is part of going out - so we're staying in'*. BBC News. [Online]. Available from: <<https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-59054772>> [Accessed 15.11.2024].

Garland, D. (1996) The Limits of the Sovereign State: Strategies of Crime Control in Contemporary Society. *British Journal of Criminology*, 36, pp. 445-471.

Hadfield, P., Lister, S. and Traynor, P. (2009) This town's a different town today. *Criminology & Criminal Justice*. [Online]. 9 (4), pp. 465–485. Available from <<https://doi.org/10.1177/1748895809343409>> [Accessed 01.11.2024].

Haleem, M.S., Lee, W.D., Ellison, M. and Bannister, J. (2020) The 'Exposed' Population, Violent Crime in Public Space and the Night-time Economy in Manchester, UK. *European Journal on Criminal Policy and Research*. [Online]. 27 (3), pp. 335-352. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10610-020-09452-5>> [Accessed 31.10.2024].

Hinds, L. and Grabosky, P. (2010) Responsibilisation revisited: From concept to attribution in crime control. *Security Journal*, 23, pp. 95-113.

Home Affairs Committee (2022a) *Spiking (HC 967, 2021-2022)*. [Online]. London: Parliamentary Copyright House of Commons 2021. Available from: <<https://committees.parliament.uk/publications/21969/documents/165662/default/>> [Accessed 14.11.2024].

Home Affairs Committee (2022b) *Spiking: Government Response to the Committee's Ninth Report of Session 2021–22 (HC 508, 2021-2022)*. [Online]. London: Parliamentary Copyright House of Commons 2021. Available

from: <<https://committees.parliament.uk/publications/22887/documents/168013/default/>> [Accessed 14.11.2024].

Home Office (2023) *Spiking: factsheet*. [Online]. Available from: <<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/spiking-factsheet/spiking-factsheet>> [Accessed 02.12.2024].

Home Office (2024) *Report: Understanding and tackling spiking (accessible)*. [Online]. Available from: <<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/understanding-and-tackling-spiking/report-understanding-and-tackling-spiking-accessible>> [Accessed 06.04.2025].

Howitt, D. and Cramer, D. (2017) *Research Methods in Psychology*. 5th ed. Harlow, England: Pearson.

Huckin, T.N (1997) Critical Discourse Analysis. In: Miller, T. ed. *Functional Approaches to Written Text: Classroom Applications*. Washington, DC: United States Information Agency, pp. 87-92.

Hughes, K. and Bellis, M. (2003) *Safer Nightlife in the North West of England*. Liverpool, UK: Liverpool John Moores University.

Ifversen, J. (2003) Text, discourse, concept: approaches to textual analysis. *Kontur–Tidsskrift for Kulturstudier*, 7 (1), pp. 60-69.

Ison, J., Wilson, I., and Hooker, L. (2024) *Schoolies means more drink spiking warnings. Why is the burden still on women to stay safe?* [Online]. The Conversation. Available from: <<https://theconversation.com/schoolies-means-more-drink-spiking-warnings-why-is-the-burden-still-on-women-to-stay-safe-243030#:~:text=Yet%20public%20messaging%20about%20drink,do%20it%20%E2%80%93%20from%20the%20story>> [Accessed 24.11.2024].

Janks, H. (1997) Critical discourse analysis as a research tool. *Discourse: studies in the cultural politics of education*, 18 (3), pp. 329-342.

Johnson, O., Andrew, B., Walker, D., Morgan, S. and Aldren, A. (2014) British university students' attitudes towards noise-induced hearing loss caused by nightclub attendance. *The Journal of Laryngology & Otology*. [Online]. 128 (1), pp. 29-34. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022215113003241>> [Accessed 01.11.2024].

Keegan, D.A. and Bannister, S.L. (2003) Effect of colour coordination of attire with poster presentation on poster popularity. *CMAJ*, 169 (12), pp. 1291-1292.

Kress, G. (1990) Critical Discourse Analysis. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*. [Online]. 11 (1), pp. 84-99. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0267190500001975>> [Accessed 18.02.2025].

Lewis, R. and McBride, A. (2024) Fear, "Discomfort", Anger, and Shame in the Night-Time Economy: Women's Responses to Unwanted Sexual Intrusions. *Violence Against Women*. [Online]. 0 (0). Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/10778012241259719>> [Accessed 25.02.2025].

Lipscombe, S. (2023) Spiking. *House of Commons Library Briefing*. [Online]. London: House of Commons Library. Available from: <<https://news.npcc.police.uk/releases/police-target-night-time-economy-to-tackle-spiking>> [Accessed 06.04.2025].

LoBue, V. and DeLoache, J.S. (2011) Pretty in pink: The early development of gender-stereotyped colour preferences. *British Journal of Developmental Psychology*, 29 (3), pp. 656-667.

Marchioni, M. (2016) *The Relationship of UK University Students with Alcohol: Binge Drinking and its Risks*. Master's degree thesis, University of Bologna.

Metropolitan Police (2024a) *How spiking can make you feel*. [Online]. Available from: <<https://www.met.police.uk/advice/advice-and-information/spiking-advice/spiking/how-spiking-can-make-you-feel/#:~:text=As%20a%20result%2C%20you%20may,always%20believe%20and%20support%20you>> [Accessed 06.04.2025].

Metropolitan Police (2024b) *What is spiking?*. [Online]. Available from: <<https://www.met.police.uk/advice/advice-and-information/spiking-advice/spiking/what-is-spiking/#:~:text=Spiking%20and%20the%20law,-Spiking%20is%20illegal&text=Spiking%20offences%20are%20covered%20by,victim%20to%20sexually%20assault%20them>> [Accessed 15.11.2024].

Ministry of Justice (2025) *Crime and Policing Bill: Spiking factsheet (MoJ)*. Policy paper. [Online]. Available from: <<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/crime-and-policing-bill-2025-factsheets/crime-and-policing-bill-spiking-factsheet-moj#:~:text=Following%20the%20Prime%20Minister's%20statement,covers%20incidents%20of%20%E2%80%9Cspiking%E2%80%9D.>>> [Accessed 11.04.2025].

Moore, S., Shepherd, J., Perham, and Cusens, B. (2007) The prevalence of alcohol intoxication in the night-time economy. *Alcohol and alcoholism*. [Online]. 42 (6), pp. 629-634. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1093/alcalc/agn054>> [Accessed 14.11.2024].

National Police Chief's Council (2022) *Potential victims of spiking urged to report to police and get tested quickly as nearly 5,000 reports of spiking are made within a year*. [Online]. Available from : <<https://news.npcc.police.uk/releases/potential-victims-of-spiking-urged-to-report-to-police-and-get-tested-quickly-as-nearly-5-000-reports-of-spiking-are-made-within-a-year>> [Accessed 15.11.2024].

Nicholls, E. (2017) 'Dulling it down a bit': managing visibility, sexualities and risk in the Night Time Economy in Newcastle, UK. *Gender, Place & Culture*. [Online]. 24 (2), pp. 260-273. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1080/0966369X.2017.1298575>> [Accessed 04.12.2024].

Nicholls, E. (2022) 'Everywhere' or 'Over There'? Managing and Spatialising the Perceived Risks of Gender-Based Violence on a Girls' Night Out. In: Bows, H. and Fileborn, B. eds. *Geographies of Gender-Based Violence*. Bristol, UK: Bristol University Press, pp. 36-49.

Nicholls, E.M.L (2015) *Running the tightrope: negotiating femininities in the night time economy in Newcastle*. Ph.D. Thesis, Newcastle University.

NPCC (2024a) *Police target night-time economy to tackle spiking*. [Online]. Available from: <<https://news.npcc.police.uk/releases/police-target-night-time-economy-to-tackle-spiking>> [Accessed 06.04.2025].

NPCC (2024b) *Violence Against Women and Girls*. [Online]. Available from: <<https://www.npcc.police.uk/our-work/violence-against-women-and-girls/>> [Accessed 06.04.2025].

O'Brien, K., Hobbs, D. and Westmarland, L. (2009) *Negotiating violence and gender: security and the night time economy in the UK*. Springer: New York.

O'Leary, K. (2021) *The Essential Guide to Doing Your Research Project*. 4th edition. London: SAGE.

Olszewski, D. (2009) Sexual assaults facilitated by drugs or alcohol. *Drugs: Education, Prevention and Policy*. [Online]. 16 (1), pp. 39-52. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1080/09687630802128756>> [Accessed 05.12.2024].

Phillips, J. (2025) *Jess Phillips says there's 'no place' where violence against women 'doesn't happen' - as spiking to become new offence*. Sky News. [Online]. Available from: <<https://news.sky.com/story/jess-phillips-says-there-is-no-place-without-violence-against-women-as-new-law-to-make-spiking-a-criminal-offence-13314031>> [Accessed 11.04.2025].

Phipps, A. and Smith, G. (2012) Violence against women students in the UK: time to take action. *Gender and Education*, (24) 4, pp. 357-373.

Randolph, J. (2009) A Guide to Writing the Dissertation Literature Review, *Practical Assessment, Research and Evaluation*. 14 (1), p. 13.

Richardson, J.E. (2006) *Analysing newspapers: an approach from critical discourse analysis*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan

Roberts, M. (2006) From 'creative city' to 'no-go areas'— The expansion of the night-time economy in British town and city centres. *Cities*. [Online]. 23 (5), pp. 331-338. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2006.05.001>> [Accessed 22.02.2025].

Sheard, S. (2011) 'Anything Could Have Happened': Women, the Night-time Economy, Alcohol and Drink Spiking. *Sociology*. [Online]. 45 (4), pp. 619-633. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/0038038511406596>> [Accessed 15.11.2024].

Simpson, P. (1993) *Language, Ideology and Point of View*. London: Routledge.

Stanko, E. A. (2008) The Case of Fearful Women: Gender, Personal Safety and Fear of Crime. *Women & Criminal Justice*. [Online]. 4 (1), pp. 117-135. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1300/J012v04n01_06> [Accessed 05.12.2024].

Stephenson, L., Tzani, C., Loannou, M., Synnott, J., Williams, T.J.V. and Morelli, M. (2023) 'No One Believed Me, and I Have No proof': An Exploration into the Experiences of Spiking Victims. *Deviant Behaviour*. [Online]. 45 (5), pp. 642-655. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1080/01639625.2023.2260924>> [Accessed 15.11.2024].

Stevenson, D. (2018) Feminism and its places: Women, leisure and the night-time economy. In: Mansfield, L., Caudwell, J., Wheaton, B. eds. *The Palgrave Handbook of Feminism and Sport, Leisure and Physical Education*. London: Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 557-569.

Sunshine, J. and Tyler, T.R (2003) The Role of Procedural Justice and Legitimacy in Shaping Public Support for Policing. *Law and Society Review*. 37 (3), pp. 513-547.

Swan, S. C., Lasky, N. V., Fisher, B. S., Woodbrown, V. D., Bonsu, J. E., Schramm, A. T., Warren, P. R., Coker, A. L. and Williams, C. M. (2017). Just a dare or unaware? Outcomes and motives of drugging ("drink spiking") among

students at three college campuses. *Psychology of Violence*. [Online]. 7 (2), pp. 253–264. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1037/vio0000060>> [Accessed 03.12.2024].

Tenorio, E.H. (2011) Critical discourse analysis, an overview. *Nordic journal of English studies*. [Online]. 10 (1), pp. 183-210. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.35360/njes.247>> [Accessed 25.02.2025].

Tokle, R., Buvik, K, Stefansen, K. and Solstad, G.M. (2023) Safety strategies, status positioning and gendered double standards: adolescents' narratives of sexualised risk in alcohol intoxication contexts. *Journal of Youth Studies*. [Online]. 27 (6), pp. 835-850. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1080/13676261.2023.2174010>> [Accessed 05.04.2025].

UK Government (2024) *PM pledges joint action to keep women and girls safe at night*. [Online]. GOV.UK. Available from: <<https://www.gov.uk/government/news/pm-pledges-joint-action-to-keep-women-and-girls-safe-at-night>> [Accessed 06.12.2024].

UN Women UK (2021) *Prevalence and Reporting of Sexual Harassment in UK Public Spaces*. [Online]. UN Women UK. Available from: <https://www.unwomenuk.org/site/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/APPG-UN-Women-Sexual-Harassment-Report_Updated.pdf> [Accessed 25.02.2025].

Vale Pires, C. (2024) Sexual terrorism in the post-pandemic nightlife? A feminist critical discourse analysis of the needle spiking media coverage. *Crime, Media, Culture*. [Online]. 0 (0). Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/17416590241302704>> [Accessed 06.04.2025].

van Dijk, T.A. (1993) Principles of critical discourse analysis. *Discourse & society*, 4 (2), pp. 249-283.

van Dijk, T.A. (2006) *Principles of Critical Discourse Analysis*. Amsterdam: University of Amsterdam.

van Dijk, T.A. (2007) Macro contexts. In: Scheu, D. and Saura, J. eds. *Discourse and international relations*. Lausanne, Switzerland: Peter Lang, pp. 3-26.

van Dijk, T.A. (2009) Critical discourse studies: A sociocognitive approach. In: Wodak, R. and Meyer, M. eds. *Methods of Critical Discourse Studies*. Los Angeles: SAGE, pp. 62-85.

van Dijk, T.A. (2011) *Discourse studies: a multidisciplinary introduction*. 2nd edition. Thousand Oaks, California: Sage Publications.

van Dijk, T.A. (2015) Critical Discourse Analysis. In: Tannen, D., Hamilton, H.E. and Schiffrin, D. eds. *The Handbook of Discourse Analysis*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, Inc, pp. 466-485.

Van Teijlingen, E. and Hundley, V. (2001) The importance of pilot studies. *Social research update*, (35), pp. 1-4.

Vartanian, T.P. (2011) *Secondary Data Analysis*. New York: Oxford University Press.

Walker, A., Barton, E., Parry, B. and Snowdon, L. (2023) *PREVENTING SEXUAL VIOLENCE IN THE NIGHT TIME ECONOMY: ENCOURAGING MEN TO BE ACTIVE BYSTANDERS*. [Online]. Wales: Violence Prevention Unit. Available from: <<https://www.violencepreventionwales.co.uk/cms-assets/research/Preventing-Sexual-Harassment-in-the-Night-Time-Economy-SafeToSay-Phase-Two-Evaluation-Report.pdf>> [Accessed 25.02.2025].

Walklate, S. (2017) Gender, violence and the fear of crime: Women as fearing subjects? In: Lee, M. and Mythen, G. *The Routledge International Handbook on Fear of Crime*. London: Routledge, pp. 222-235.

Watts, R., Linke, S., Murray, E. and Barker, C. (2015) Calling the shots: Young professional women's relationship with alcohol. *Feminism & Psychology*. [Online]. 25 (2), pp. 219-234. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/0959353515571670>> [Accessed 02.12.2024].

Widdowson, H.G. (2004) *Text, Context, Pretext. Critical Issues in Discourse Analysis*. Oxford: Blackwell.

Wimmer, J. and Quandt, T. (2007) LIVING IN THE RISK SOCIETY: An interview with Ulrich Beck. *Journalism Studies*. [Online]. 7 (2), pp. 336-347. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1080/14616700600645461>> [Accessed 04.12.2024].

Wodak, R. (2002) Aspects of critical discourse analysis. *Zeitschrift für angewandte Linguistik*, 36 (10), pp. 5-31.

Wodak, R. (2014) Critical discourse analysis. In: Leung, C. and Street, B.V. eds. *The Routledge Companion to English Studies*. London: Routledge, pp. 302-316.

Wodak, R. and Meyer, M. (2016) *Methods of Critical Discourse Studies*. 3rd edition. Los Angeles: SAGE.